

ELIXIR
Data Platform
2024-26
Work Plan

Abstract

The ELIXIR Data Platform has successfully established a robust community interested in various aspects of life science data, and defined sustainable Core Data Resources (CDRs) of exceptional quality. The Platform is now concentrating on developing and improving methods for brokering data contributions, promoting innovative credit attribution systems, and enhancing and automating data curation practices for FAIRification of existing data. It seeks to expand its work on sustainability to more diverse biological databases and to create a diverse ecosystem of Node Data Resources, fostering collaborations through its extensive ELIXIR member network, while aligning efforts globally and ensuring impactful contributions to European research innovation.

This document shows the work plan version as approved by the ELIXIR Board in November 2023.

About this document

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1. Objectives and relation to the Scientific Programme

The ELIXIR Data Platform has been successful in creating a vibrant group of people interested in all aspects of life science data, from generation and curation to storage, archiving, use and reuse. It has achieved its first mission and defined a sustainable and well-funded collection of Core Data Resources (CDRs) that represent the gold standard on the world stage. It has more recently begun developing and defining tools to boost data integration and curation capacities and helped grow a coordinated ecosystem of Node Data Resources within ELIXIR. As the demand for data, its storage and interpretation continues to grow and change, it is appropriate for the Data Platform to collectively adapt and look to the next chapter to address the technical and societal challenges of users and life sciences researchers in Europe.

Looking to the future, the Data Platform will focus on three key themes; strengthening data connectivity and accessibility through brokering; recognition and credit attribution for contributors; and FAIRification of existing data. It will also work to support a greater diversity of data resources by defining their context, quality and unique challenges within the ELIXIR framework. Key to achieving this, is its ability to leverage the robust network of ELIXIR members — reachable through Platforms, Communities and Focus Groups — to connect data users, contributors and resources across Nodes while fostering collaborative discussions and leveraging technological advancements.

Thematic areas

Connecting and brokering Node contributions to ELIXIR data resources

- Facilitate connection between ELIXIR data resources and contributors within its diverse Nodes.
- Investigate various methods for brokering data transfer, aggregation, and discovery, considering technology, standards, and relevant communities.
- Establish a forum for the Data Platform and ELIXIR stakeholders, fostering interactions with the data management community.
- Explore organisational (e.g. training) and technical mechanisms to provide best practices and potentially create specialised training paths.

Recognition and credit attribution of researcher contributions to data resources

- Enhance recognition and credit for activities contributing to data curation, annotation, and expansion in relevant repositories and knowledge bases.
- Utilise the APICURON infrastructure to extend credit attribution beyond traditional biocuration to areas such as registries, code contributions, and data management.
- Develop a service that links mapped data citations and credits, integrating them into citation networks like OpenAIRE KG.
- Investigate broader applications of this approach, including crediting trainers in Training Platform activities, with consideration for sociological implications.

Scalable curation support from the long tail of biological data (FAIRification of Data)

- Address the challenge of underutilised data by implementing FAIRification methods, especially for supplementary data files and long-tail contents in scientific reports.
- Focus on specific biological and FAIR-relevant entities to design curation-support services, enhancing Knowledge Management and Delivery skills for Core Data Resources and Community Databases.
- Explore standards, best practices, and technologies to support FAIRification efforts, such as using JATS, DCAT, RO-Crate, and semantic web tools.
- Define new FAIR annotations for lesser-studied entities, aligned with ELIXIR's thematic priorities.
- Develop strategies for implementing FAIR annotations and normalising content at scale, including coordination with publishers.

Establishing and shaping the landscape of Core and Community Biological Databases across ELIXIR (in a Global Context)

- Collaborate with ELIXIR members, CDR maintainers, Node Coordinators, and EuropePMC to define the landscape of core and community data resources.
- Adapt the analytics and metrics used to assess Core Data Resources and ELIXIR Deposition Databases, to account for changing usage patterns and mechanisms.
- Establish objective criteria and metrics for identifying and labelling diverse community databases, involving ELIXIR Communities and Node Service Delivery Plans.
- Extend the “data universe” to encompass overlooked content, including supplementary data and preprints.
- Engage in discussions with stakeholders to contextualise the overall landscape analysis from a global perspective.

In conclusion, this multifaceted initiative focuses on advancing data connectivity and accessibility, recognition of effort, and FAIRification within the established ELIXIR framework. By fostering collaborations, implementing cutting-edge technologies, and aligning with international stakeholders, ELIXIR Data Platform aims to unlock the potential of underutilised data resources and promote greater innovation and scientific advancement, ensuring its contributions are of the highest value to the European research community.

2. Partnership

Contributors to the work programme are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Overview of involved institutions.

Node	Institution	Abbreviation
BE	Université libre de Bruxelles (Free University of Brussels)	BE-ULB
BE	Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie (Flemish Institute for Biotechnology)	BE-VIB
CH	Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics	CH-SIB
DE	Forschungszentrum Jülich (Jülich Research Center)	DE-FZJ
DE	Heidelberg Institute for Theoretical Studies	DE-HITS
DE	Leibniz-Institut für Pflanzengenetik und Kulturpflanzenforschung (Leibniz Institut for Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research) (IPK)	DE-IPK
EL	ELIXIR Hub	ELIXIR-HUB
EM	European Molecular Biology Laboratory - European Bioinformatics Institute	EMBL-EBI
ES	Centre for Genomic Regulation	ES-CRG
FR	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (National Center for Scientific Research)	FR-CNRS
UK	University of Cambridge	UK-UCAM
UK	University of Oxford	UK-UOXF
GR	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	GR-AUTH
GR	Athena Research Center	GR-ATHENA
IT	Università degli Studi di Bologna (University of Bologna)	IT-UNIBO
IT	Università degli Studi di Padova (University of Padua)	IT-UNIPD
IT	Università degli Studi di Roma Tor Vergata (University of Rome Tor Vergata)	IT-UNIROMA2
NO	University of Oslo	NO-UiO
SE	Chalmers University	SE-CTH
SE	Uppsala University	SE-UU
SI	Univerza v Ljubljani (University of Ljubljana)	SI-ULJU

3. Work Package descriptions

Work Package 1 - Management and Coordination

WP 1	Lead Partner: CH-SIB DE-HITS IT-UNIPD	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
CH-SIB - Patrick Ruch		
DE-HITS - Ulrike Wittig		
IT-UNIPD - Silvio Tosatto		
ELIXIR-HUB - Fabio Liberante, Gavin Farrell		
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective Statement: The ELIXIR Data Platform ExCo will carry out management and coordination activities during the 2024-2026 work plan to ensure efficient operation and collaboration within the Platform. • Monthly Coordination Calls: The ExCo will organise and conduct monthly coordination calls to foster effective communication and collaboration among platform members, ensuring timely information exchange and progress updates. • Annual Face-to-Face Meeting: The ExCo will arrange an annual face-to-face meeting, providing a platform for in-depth discussions, strategic planning, and decision-making to drive the Platform's goals and initiatives. • Joint Platform Activities: The ExCo will facilitate joint activities among Platform members, promoting collaboration and knowledge sharing to leverage collective expertise and resources. This will likely combine with regular F2F. • Oversight and Responsibility: The ExCo will be responsible for overseeing the implementation of the work plan, monitoring progress, and ensuring that objectives are met within the designated time frame. Monthly ExCo only meeting. • Reporting and Stakeholder Engagement: The ExCo will provide regular reporting and progress updates to the ELIXIR governance bodies and relevant stakeholders, fostering transparency and accountability. • Partnership and Collaboration: The ExCo will actively engage with external partners and organisations, seeking opportunities for collaborations and resource-sharing to enhance the Platform's capabilities and impact. • Evaluation and Improvement: The ExCo will review and evaluate the outcomes of Platform activities, identifying areas for improvement and proposing necessary adjustments to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the platform's operations. 		
<p>Description of Work</p> <p>Activity 1 - Face-to-Face Meetings: Alternating between hosts and jointly with other Platforms <i>(leads: CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig), IT-UNIPD (Silvio Tosatto); members: ELIXIR-Hub (Fabio Liberante, Gavin Farrell) , M1 - M36)</i></p> <p>This activity involves organising an annual face-to-face meeting for the ELIXIR Data Platform members in loose collaboration with one of the other ELIXIR Platforms. The meetings will rotate among the ExCo and their member states as hosts. The purpose of these meetings is to provide a dedicated platform for in-depth discussions, strategic planning, and decision-making. The ExCo will collaborate with the Hub to plan and execute the meeting effectively. The agenda will be designed to address key topics related to the Platform</p>		

goals, initiatives, progress, challenges, and opportunities. The meeting will also provide a unique opportunity for Platform members to interact in person, fostering stronger working relationships and promoting a sense of unity within the Platform and across ELIXIR. The ExCo will ensure that the meeting outcomes are documented and disseminated.

Activity 2 - Monthly TC

(leads: CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig), IT-UNIPD (Silvio Tosatto); members: ELIXIR-Hub (Fabio Liberante, Gavin Farrell), M1 - M36)

The monthly teleconferences (TC) are a crucial element of the coordination and collaboration strategy of the ELIXIR Data Platform. These regular virtual meetings will provide a forum for effective communication, information exchange and activity among Platform members. The ExCo will oversee the scheduling of these TCs and develop an agenda for each.

The format of these TCs will alternate between two main focuses:

- **Status Reports from the Work Packages** within the Platform. Each Work Package lead will present updates on their respective activities, progress made, challenges encountered, and milestones achieved. This segment aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the ongoing initiatives within the Platform, facilitating transparency and alignment among members.
- **Highlight Presentations of General Interest** related to emerging trends and practices in the realm of data management and analysis. During these sessions, members and invited guests will have the opportunity to share insights, developments, or innovative practices related to data management, analysis, sharing, or any other relevant topics. These presentations are intended to foster knowledge exchange, encourage cross-pollination of ideas, and promote discussions that can inspire new collaborations or improvements within the platform.

For each TC, the ExCo will coordinate with the presenters, ensuring that they have the necessary time and resources to prepare their updates or presentations. The ExCo will develop a detailed agenda for each call, specifying the topics, presenters, and time allocations for each segment. The ExCo will also moderate the discussions and encourage active participation. The ExCo will work to ensure active and fair participation from all members, encouraging open discussions and idea sharing during these calls. Meeting minutes will be recorded during each TC, capturing the key points discussed, action items identified, and decisions made. These minutes will be shared with all Platform members to provide a comprehensive overview of the discussions and outcomes. This approach aims to maintain engagement, encourage collaboration, and support the achievement of the ELIXIR Data Platform's objectives.

Activity 3 - ExCo Monthly TC

(leads: CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig), IT-UNIPD (Silvio Tosatto); members: ELIXIR-Hub (Fabio Liberante, Gavin Farrell), M1 - M36)

This activity specifically refers to the ExCo only monthly TC. The ExCo members will convene on a monthly basis to discuss matters related to the management, coordination, and oversight of the ELIXIR Data Platform. This includes reviewing progress against the work plan, evaluating the effectiveness of ongoing activities, and identifying any areas requiring additional attention or adjustments. The ExCo monthly teleconference will serve as a crucial mechanism for decision-making and strategy refinement.

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D1.1	Annual report 1 - on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	DE-HITS	M13
D1.2	Annual report 2 - on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	IT-UNIPD	M25
D1.3	End Report	CH-SIB	M36

D1.4	Drafted project plan for the next funding cycle in 2027-2028 ELIXIR Programme	DE-HITS	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M1.1	Annual Data Platform meeting 1	DE-HITS	M12
M1.2	Annual Data Platform meeting 2	IT-UNIPD	M24
M1.3	Annual Data Platform meeting 3	CH-SIB	M36

Work Package 2 - Connecting and brokering Node contributions to ELIXIR Data resources

WP 2	Lead Partner: EMBL-EBI BE-VIB	
	Start month- End month: Mo1-M36	
WP Partnership		
BE-VIB - Flora D'Anna		
EMBL-EBI - Ugis Sarkans		
EMBL-EBI - Zahra Waheed		
SE-UU - Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström		
CH-SIB - Monique Zahn		
NO-UiO - Sveinung Gundersen		
CH-SIB - Séverine Duvaud		
DE-FZJ - Sebastian Beier		
DE-HITS - Ulrike Wittig		
DE-IPK - Daniel Arend		
EMBL-EBI - Claire O'Donovan		
EMBL-EBI - Guy Cochrane		
ES-CRG - Teresa D'Altri		
UK-UOXF - Allyson Lister		
UK-UOXF - Philippe Rocca-Serra		
GR-AUTH - Christos Ouzounis		
IT-UNIROMA2 - Luana Licata		
NO-UiO - Federico Bianchini		
SE-UU - Niclas Jareborg		
SI-ULJU - Brane Leskošek		
Objectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connect ELIXIR data resources with data contributors in the various ELIXIR nodes. • Explore and compare different ways of brokering the data transfer, aggregation and discovery, in terms of technology, standards and communities, for both CDRs and community databases. • Provide a discussion forum between the Data platform and various ELIXIR stakeholders such as the data management community. • Explore different organisational (e.g. events) and technical mechanisms and provide best practices, with the possibility of establishing dedicated training paths in the field. 		

Description of Work

Activity 1 Landscape of Data brokering

(leads: EMBL-EBI (Zahra Waheed), DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig); members: BE-VIB (Flora D'Anna), SE-UU (Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström), IT-UNIROMA2 (Luana Licata), GR-AUTH (Christos Ouzounis), SI-ULJU (Brane Leskošek), DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig), CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), CH-SIB (Monique Zahn), CH-SIB (Séverine Duvaud), DE-FZJ (Sebastian Beier), DE-IPK (Daniel Arend), EMBL-EBI (Ugis Sarkans), NO-UiO (Federico Bianchini), EMBL-EBI (Claire O'Donovan), M1 - M36)

Data brokering is the act of submitting data to one or more databases on behalf of another person/institute. It involves the coordination between data producers in an institution of an ELIXIR node, which provides data management support, and deposition databases like the ELIXIR Deposition Database (EDD). Moreover, data producers might use platforms or technical services (e.g. brokerage platforms) provided by the Node to collect and prepare (meta)data for publication into databases. Often, multi-omics studies would also require references among several datasets published in different databases to preserve the relations among data (data linkage). For any of these use cases, connections are based on data exchange formats and the mapping of metadata schemas. This task will build on and continue the work from the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project T1.2 on "Models for brokering data to ELIXIR Deposition Databases", and in particular on multi-omics studies. The focus will be on the definition of "brokering" and landscape analysis of ELIXIR data resources and their existing requirements for data linkage and submission of multi-omics studies.

Plan of work

- We will select data deposition databases relevant to this work package. While ELIXIR CDR and EDD are already of interest, we will also consider discipline-specific repositories such as those highlighted in CONVERGE T1.2 (see Activity 3), the eDAL!-PGP repository and others. We will identify a point of contact who possesses knowledge and expertise about the selected repositories for this project.
- Compile a comprehensive list of the various types of data brokering involved in the transfer of data from data producers to deposition databases, via a broker or a brokerage platform. To accomplish this, we will leverage the knowledge and expertise of the point of contact for the selected repositories and collaborate with research data management (RDM) professionals within the RDM Community.
- Analysis of requirements for data linkage and data submission for each selected deposition database. Starting from the information available in FAIRsharing, a landscape of the deposition databases' capability to receive data via a broker or a brokerage platform will be made, with a special focus on multi-omics data submission.
- When needed, necessary updates in FAIRsharing will be communicated to the owner of the record in the platform. A field will be added to FAIRsharing to capture "brokering solutions requirements" in the database registry.
- We will collect user requirements from data producers/brokers, specifically focusing on multi-omics submission, to determine their desired functionalities in the system. Subsequently, we will formalise these requirements as recommendations for technical and process improvements in deposition databases (Activity 2).

Outcome

- Definitions of different types of brokering
- Landscape of the current best practices and capability to receive data via a broker or a brokerage platform for selected repositories, with a focus on ELIXIR Nodes
- Updated FAIRsharing Collections with records about capability to receive data via a broker or a brokerage platform of databases linked to their data exchange formats, metadata schemas and brokering solutions requirements
- Collection of user requirements from data producers/brokers, specifically focusing on multi-omics submission, to determine their desired functionalities in the system

Activity 2 - Defining best practices for data brokering

(leads: BE-VIB (Flora D'Anna), DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig); members: UK-UOXF (Allyson Lister), SE-UU (Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström), ES-CRG (Teresa D'Altri), IT-UNIROMA2 (Luana Licata), GR-AUTH (Christos Ouzounis), SI-ULJU (Brane Leskošek), CH-SIB (Monique Zahn), NO-UiO (Sveinung Gundersen), EMBL-EBI (Ugis Sarkans), M1 - M36)

Data brokering can be done on different levels of operational complexity using different data exchange formats and metadata standards. In this task best practices and guidelines for data brokering will be defined to support repositories in developing or improving data submission and data linkage.

Plan of work

- Build focus group of brokering experts from Data platform members, repository representatives, and members of the ELIXIR RDM Community to align users requirements (Activity 1) with repositories' capability to receive submission via broker or brokerage platforms.
- Formalise current best practices for brokers and repositories in appropriate knowledge resources (e.g. RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook)
- Define ideal and streamlined way for brokering services (maturity model)
- Analysis of existing literature and guidelines about data brokering including the results of the landscape analysis in WP1.2
- Define a FAIRsharing Collection that supports the ELIXIR data brokering marketplace, offering an overview of ELIXIR repositories, data exchange formats and metadata standards
- Continuous on-boarding of ELIXIR data resources in FAIRsharing, for the description of the data resource and the standards used

Outcome

- Recommendations for technical and process improvements for brokering services in deposition databases
- Publication of best practices and guidelines e.g. on the RDMkit Task page and as a recipe in the FAIR Cookbook "Data brokering"
- Data brokering maturity model (example: [ELIXIR Maturity Model for Pathogen Data Platforms](#))
- ELIXIR website containing ELIXIR data brokering market place recommendations
- FAIRsharing Collection of ELIXIR repositories and their characteristics and requirements

Activity 3 - Implementation use cases of best practices

(leads: BE-VIB (Flora D'Anna), SE-UU (Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström); members: BE-VIB (Bert Droesbeke), UK-UOXF (Philippe Rocca-Serra), DE-FZJ (Sebastian Beier), NO-UiO (Sveinung Gundersen), DE-IPK (Daniel Arend), UK-UOXF (Munazah Andrabi), CH-SIB (Sverine Duvaud), EMBL-EBI (Ugis Sarkans), EMBL-EBI (Claire O'Donovan), M1 - M36)

This activity will build on the work of activity 2 (WP2.2) and the three data brokering scenarios analysed in the [ELIXIR-CONVERGE project \(WP1 T1.2\)](#), including the results from the [BioHackathon 2022 project 27](#). The work will initially explore and further develop solutions based on the ISA abstract model and its implementation as ISA-JSON, which were used in ELIXIR-CONVERGE for brokering multi-omics studies. Then, the feasibility of extending the same approach to the other scenarios will be investigated. Following the work of activity 1 (WP2.1) and activity 2 (WP2.2), additional use cases will be selected to explore how the ISA-based solution can be expanded to support the proposed best practices for a wider range of domains/techniques and corresponding ELIXIR deposition databases. The activity will also evaluate a selection of complementary technologies (including RO-Crate) to develop a high-level technical proof of concept showcasing the feasibility and functionality of at least one of the representative use cases.

Plan of work

- Explore applicability of the brokering approach based on ISA-JSON to other scenarios from CONVERGE WP1 T1.2
- Based on the results of WP2.1 and WP2.2, evaluate how the brokering approach based on ISA-JSON can be used to support the defined best practices
- Explore the possibility of combining the ISA-JSON approach with RO-Crate technology as method for transferring metadata and data to deposition databases
 - See FAIR Cookbook example "[Packaging ISA as a Research Object \(RO\)](#)"
 - Create a comprehensive library of shared examples, references and tools

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Define RO-Crate profiles and ISA-JSON schemas to simplify RO-Crate production/consumption ● Support the implementation of selected scenarios by defining a high-level technical proof of concept to showcase the feasibility and functionality of the selected approach <p>Outcome</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● High-level technical proof of concept to showcase the feasibility and functionality of the proposed approach for data brokering (D3.1) - Responsible SE - Uppsala University - M36 ● Publication of Data brokering scenarios and use cases as RDMkit Tool assembly pages, and in a citable recipe in the FAIR Cookbook (D3.2) - Responsible VIB - M36 			
Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D2.1	Description of landscape analysis including collection of user and repository requirements	EMBL-EBI	M18
D2.2	Description of best practices in appropriate knowledge resources (e.g. RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, FAIRsharing)	BE-VIB	M24
D2.3	Maturity model for data brokering services	BE-VIB	M36
D2.4	A detailed description for the high-level technical proof of concept, demonstrating the feasibility and functionality of the proposed approach for data brokering	SE-UU	M36
D2.5	Publication of the proposed solution(s) for data brokering in appropriate knowledge resources (e.g. RDMkit Tool assembly page and a FAIR Cookbook recipe)	BE-VIB	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M2.1	Definition of the parameters for the landscape analysis	EMBL-EBI	M8
M2.2	Writing event	CH-SIB	M20
M2.3	Following the work of activity 1 and activity 2 additional use cases (beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP1 Task 2) have been selected to support further explorations into how the ISA-based solution can be expanded to support the emerging best practices for a wider range of domains/techniques and corresponding ELIXIR deposition databases	NO-UiO	M30

Work Package 3 - Recognition and credit attribution of research contributions to data resources

WP 3	Lead Partner: IT-UNIPD	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
IT-UPD - Damiano Piovesan		
SE-CTH - Mihail Anton		
UK-UCAM - Valerie Wood		
CH-SIB - Patrick Ruch		
FR-CNRS - Alban Gaignard		
GR-ATHENA - Thanasis Vergoulis		
IT-UNIPD - Silvio Tosatto		
DE-HITS - Ulrike Wittig		
GR-AUTH - Christos Ouzounis		
GR-CERTH - Fotis Psomopoulos		
IT-UNIPD - Adel Bouhraoua		
UK-UOXF - Allyson Lister		
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the recognition and credit attribution of activities which curate, annotate or otherwise contribute to the increase of data in relevant resources such as knowledge bases. • Leverage the work of APICURON to provide an infrastructural component to use in different contexts beyond more traditional biocuration activities (e.g. knowledge bases), ranging from ELIXIR registries (e.g. bio.tools, RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, FAIRsharing), to code contributions (e.g. in GitHub) and data management/stewardship (e.g. data brokering). The resulting service will link the mapped data citations and credits for primary contributions to citation networks (e.g. OpenAIRE KG). Moreover, it will explore the possibility to generalise the approach and employ it in other contexts such as crediting trainers in Training Platform activities. In addition to the technological component, it will explore the “sociological” implications for the “person infrastructure”, including career pathways, fostering adoption and user engagement (e.g. with gamification techniques). 		
<p>Description of Work</p> <p>Activity 1 - Technical developments for recognition <i>(lead: IT-UNIPD (Silvio Tosatto); members: FR-CNRS (Alban Gaignard), SE-CTH (Mihail Anton), M1 - M36)</i></p> <p>This task will continue the technical developments for implementing recognition and credit attribution mechanisms. The APICURON platform, currently restricted to curated databases, will be expanded to cover a wider range of activities, based on user input. On-boarding of additional ELIXIR resources will lead to technical changes, as well as requests for additional features supported by this task. A major step will be the establishment of a prototype mechanism for harvesting GitHub contributions on a small subset of selected profiles, e.g., training materials developed using the GitHub template established by the Training Platform.</p>		

The visualisation of additional statistics for curators both on the APICURON website and via widgets for third-party websites will be supported based on the outputs of WP3.2. In addition, work will be carried out to create appropriate Bioschemas entities for information in APICURON in order to connect to the OpenAIRE knowledge-graph.

Plan of work

- Continuous on-boarding of ELIXIR data resources in APICURON
- APICURON linking relevant information from FAIRsharing (e.g. resource description)
- Expanding technical functionalities of APICURON based on new resources
- Annotating APICURON entries with Bioschemas
- Harvesting data from GitHub
- Visualisation of additional statistics for curators
- Establishing an embeddable widget (that people can use in their public profile pages, which links to their corresponding profile page on APICURON)

Outcome

- APICURON established as ELIXIR's service for recognition and credit attribution, with a wide range of connected data resources
- Expanded people and resource profiles providing rich statistics promoting engagement implemented

Activity 2 - Engagement and gamification for recognition

(leads: IT-UNIPD (Silvio Tosatto); members: UK-UCAM (Valerie Wood), UK-UOXF (Allyson Lister), GR-CERTH (Fotis Psomopoulos), M1 - M36)

This task focuses on the sociological aspects related to recognition and credit attribution. It will define strategies for implementing gamification effectively, through the evaluation of use cases and establishment of guidelines. The work will span two orthogonal views, from the resources implementing recognition and credit attribution mechanisms (resource view, e.g. PomBase) as well as the individual contributors (people view, e.g. curators). The resource view will help define best practices for the granularity of events to be captured in recognition and how to attribute credit for them. The people view will instead focus on how to promote engagement via gamification, i.e. how to build meaningful statistics based on the captured events.

Plan of work

- Evaluate use cases for APICURON resources
- Landscape analysis of resources for defining granularity of tracked contributions (resource view)
- Strategies for promoting engagement and gamification (people view)
- Defining relevant statistics for recognition

Outcome

- Best practices for integrating resources into APICURON established (resource view)
- Guidelines for maximising contributor engagement by leveraging gamification principles (people view)

Activity 3 - Outreach and engagement with other initiatives

(leads: CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch); members: GR-ATHENA (Thanasis Vergoulis), GR-AUTH (Christos Ouzounis), GR-CERTH (Fotis Psomopoulos), SE-CTH (Mihail Anton), M1 - M36)

This task focuses on promoting alignment with and uptake of the recognition and credit infrastructure by other initiatives, both within and outside ELIXIR (e.g. Bionomia, LifeWatch). It will create opportunities for Community engagement by presenting the recognition work at different ELIXIR meetings (e.g. AHM, BioHackathon), and within Platforms, e.g., by aligning with related work in the contemporary activities of the Training Platform. It will also provide the necessary coordination with relevant stakeholders for alternative career assessment, including EU projects (such as STEERS, EVERSE and GraspOS) and the EOSC task force on research careers.

Plan of work

- Engage with ELIXIR Platforms and Communities
- Engage with STEERS, EVERSE and GraspOS
- Engage with EOSC task force on research careers

<p>Outcome</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> APICURON is recognized both within and outside ELIXIR as a relevant infrastructure service for recognition and credit attribution. 			
Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D3.1	Report on resources integrated in APICURON	IT-UNIPD	M36
D3.2	Demonstrator for expanded profiles providing rich statistics in APICURON	IT-UNIPD	M30
D3.3	Report on engagement and gamification strategies, describing resource and people views	IT-UNIPD	M24
D3.4	Report on uptake of APICURON as an infrastructure service	IIT-UNIPD	M36
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M3.1	Bioschemas entities for APICURON defined	FR-CNRS	M15
M3.2	Prototype for harvesting GitHub contributions implemented	SE-UU	M24
M3.3	Use cases for APICURON evaluated	IT-UNIPD	M12
M3.4	Outreach link established with relevant EU Projects (e.g. STEERS, EVERSE and GraspOS)	GR-ATHENA	M18

Work Package 4 - Scalable curation support from the long tail of biological data

WP 4	Lead Partner: CH-SIB	
	Start month- End month: Mo1-M36	
WP Partnership		
CH-SIB - Julien Gobeill		
BE-ULB - Tom Lenaerts		
EMBL-EBI - Matt Jeffryes		
EMBL-EBI - Aravind Venkatesan		
IT-UNIROMA2 - Luana Licata		
CH-SIB - Patrick Ruch		
CH-SIB - Paul van Rijen		
EMBL-EBI - Melissa Harrison		
IT-UNIBO - Emidio Capriotti		
IT-UNIBO - Paula Turina		
IT-UNIPD - Alexander Monzon		
SE-CTH - Mihail Anton		
SE-UU - Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström		
<p>The backlog of supplementary data attached to published scientific reports, as well as generalist deposited contents, the so-called long tail of data, is a potential goldmine for research. Unfortunately, these data are buried in the contents of millions of semantically poor files. This long tail of data needs FAIR-ification using automatic methods.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Select a small number of biological and FAIR-relevant entities to design curation-support services (e.g., entity normalisation and triage) to increase Knowledge Management and Delivery skills of ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Community Databases. • Explore how standards (e.g., JATS, DCAT, RO-Crate), best practices (e.g., DOME for machine learning) and technologies (e.g., search engines, semantic web) can support this FAIR-ification effort. • Define the scope of new FAIR annotations for lesser studied entities at scale (e.g., licensing models, populations, biodiversity taxons), derived from the thematic priorities of ELIXIR: biotic interactions for “biodiversity and food”, mutations for “human data” and cell lines for “cell and molecular sciences”. • Develop FAIR-ification strategies to support these novel annotations (e.g., semantic annotations, content normalisation and indexing). • Coordinate with similar efforts by publishers (e.g. Pensoft/OpenBioDiv). 		

Description of Work

Activity 1 - Coordination of literature curation challenges and practices

(leads: CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch); members: BE-ULB (Tom Lenaerts), EMBL-EBI (Matt Jeffryes), EMBL-EBI (Aravind Venkatesan), IT-UNIROMA2 (Luana Licata), CH-SIB (Paul van Rijen), EMBL-EBI (Melissa Harrison), IT-UNIBO (Emidio Capriotti), IT-UNIBO (Paula Turina), IT-UNIPD (Alexander Monzon), SE-CTH (Mihail Anton), SE-UU (Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström), M1 - M36)

The primary channel of communication in life science is and remains the literature. However, practices and standards for literature publication are evolving and a growing set of publications contains structured dataset descriptions (e.g., DOME) and links to specialised data repositories or general ones (e.g., Zenodo). Further, and although CDR and Community Databases may exhibit very heterogeneous biological interests, we aim at defining some minimal data typology shared by all data resources: paper- vs. passage-centric curation, continuous vs. session-driven curation efforts, role of supplementary data or generalist repositories in curation guidelines, and named entities as in EuropePMC/SIBiLS annotations.

Plan of work

- Survey standards (e.g. JATS, BioC, supplementary data) and practices used to support curation and annotation
- Investigate how to measure and improve the FAIR-ness of the "long tail" of literature contents
- Define the scope of new FAIR annotations for lesser studied entities at scale with Data Platform stakeholders (e.g., licensing models, populations, biodiversity taxons) and develop FAIR-ification strategies to support them (e.g., semantic annotations, content normalisation and indexing).

Outcome

- A set of recommendations to support both curated resources and standard/ontology development organisations

Activity 2 - Turning the long tail of literature and supplementary data into FAIR digital objects

(leads: CH-SIB (Julien Gobeill); members: BE-ULB (Tom Lenaerts), EMBL-EBI (Matt Jeffryes), EMBL-EBI (Aravind Venkatesan), IT-UNIROMA2 (Luana Licata), CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), CH-SIB (Paul van Rijen), EMBL-EBI (Melissa Harrison), IT-UNIBO (Emidio Capriotti), IT-UNIBO (Paula Turina), IT-UNIPD (Alexander Monzon), SE-CTH (Mihail Anton), SE-UU (Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström), M1 - M36)

This subtask aims to complement the transformational efforts focusing on the FAIR-ification of literature using semantic web technologies. The idea is to leverage on-going efforts (e.g., PDF2JATS, RO-Crate, DOME, Zenodo) to both improve FAIR archiving standards and to explore how such formats can be discovered through an index or a Knowledge Graph. First, we plan to establish a communication channel with related European initiatives. We will leverage EU research infrastructure projects, such as BiCIKL or FAIRClinical (ELIXIR-LU, CH, FR, UK), to coordinate efforts in and outside ELIXIR with lead stakeholders (e.g., CERN, LifeWatch, GBIF, GBC). Second, the task will explore how these digital objects can be made available for discovery.

Plan of work

- Align and coordinate with similar European efforts, (e.g., LifeWath ERIC, CERN, EOSC/OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph)
- Explore how semantic web standards and technologies for archiving can support the FAIR-ification of literature contents and related contents (e.g., article meta-data, supplementary data file types)

Outcome

- Organise events and workshops with related initiatives (e.g., W3C, TDWG, EOSC events)
- Develop pilot experiments to expose literature contents using the appropriate semantic web technologies
- A semantically annotated sample of Europe PMC literature and supplementary data files (e.g., spreadsheets, images, JATS/TaxPub treatments) powered with advanced search functionalities.

Activity 3 - Accessing traceable author statements from curated databases

(leads: CH-SIB (Julien Gobeill), SIB; members: SE-CTH (Mihail Anton), EMBL-EBI (Matt Jeffryes), EMBL-EBI (Aravind Venkatesan), IT-UNIROMA2 (Luana Licata), CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), CH-SIB (Paul van Rijen), SE-UU (Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström, IT-UNIPD (Alexander Monzon),) M1 - M36)

ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Community Databases tend to cross-reference articles to provide their end-users with access to the source of their knowledge. Unfortunately, the unit of evidence is generally the article, which may mean up to 20-30 pages of PDF. Such granularity is often not sufficient to efficiently access an explicit traceable author statement. However, some databases and communities (e.g. System biology, Rare diseases, Biodiversity) propose to record evidence at a finer granularity. In particular GeneRiFs (Gene Reference Into Functions) and MINT/IntAct can track evidence at the level of a unique sentence. The same applies to biotic interactions. Based on a sample of GBC, CDR and CDB (e.g., DisProt, CelloSaurus, MINT/IntAct, OLIDA), and together with WP3.1, we propose to explore how published evidence could be better captured, cross-referenced and displayed. Such a curation model will leverage methods to uniquely identify both sentences and sections in articles (e.g., Europe PMC SciLite, Biocuration Toolkit); thus evolving article and supplementary data representation standards such as JATS and BioC.

Plan of work:

- Select a sample set of curated data providers
- Analyse the feasibility of evolving curation guidelines of these data providers, including the Evidence Code Ontology (ECO), to capture higher precision textual evidence
- Explore how to represent & visualise these new types of evidence in JATS-XML contents

Outcome:

- Develop demonstrator to show how sentences/passages can be highlighted into JATS PMC files
- Write a scientific report to be submitted to JATS-Con 2025

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D4.1	A report describing best practices of literature biocuration	CH-SIB	M12
D4.2	A workshop co-located in a known forum to report on	CH-SIB	M18
D4.3	A large annotated dataset of literature	CH-SIB	M18
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M4.1	A demonstrator showing how annotations can be displayed in JATS/BioC	CH-SIB EMBL-EBI	M24

Work Package 5 - Establishing and shaping the landscape of Core and Community Biological Databases

WP 5	Lead Partner: IT-UPD, CH-SIB	
	Start month- End month: M01-M36	
WP Partnership		
IT-UNIPD - Damiano Piovesan		
CH-SIB - Julien Gobeill		
CH-SIB - Lucy Poveda		
CH-SIB - Patrick Ruch		
EMBL-EBI - Melissa Harrisson		
SE-CTH - Mihail Anton		
CH-SIB - Christophe Dessimoz		
DE-HITS - Ulrike Wittig		
EMBL-EBI - Guy Cochrane		
GR-AUTH - Christos Ouzounis		
IT-UNIPD - Silvio Tosatto		
<p>Objectives</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the ELIXIR landscape in terms of core and community data resources by working with ELIXIR members, e.g. CDR maintainers as the CDR Forum, Node Coordinators, and EuropePMC • Maintain and incrementally update the existing analytical pipeline to evaluate the Core Data Resources (CDRs) and ELIXIR Deposition Databases (EDDs) to keep up with the growth of databases as well as the universe of analytics/metrics. • Design objective criteria and metrics for the identification and labelling of more diverse community databases with the help of the ELIXIR Communities, for instance by leveraging the nodes' service delivery plans. • Explore how the data universe can be expanded to include neglected contents (e.g. supplementary data, preprints). • Maintain a dialogue with Global stakeholders (e.g. GBC, NIH) to better situate the landscape analysis in a broader context. 		
<p>Description of Work</p> <p>Activity 1 - Leverage the interactions with the Global Biodata Coalition to support the CDR and outreach <i>(leads: ELIXIR-HUB (Fabio Liberante); members: ELIXIR-HUB (Gavin Farrell), CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), IT-UNIPD (Silvio Tosatto), DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig), M1 - M36)</i></p> <p>The aim of this task is the coordination of the interactions between ELIXIR Data Platform and Global Biodata Coalition. It also includes established processes of assessment for granting CDR/EDD status and Periodic Review of existing resources.</p>		

Plan of work

- Organise regular calls/meeting with GBC
- Yearly CDR Forum call/meeting
- Provide outputs from WP5.2 and WP5.3 Deliverables to GBC stakeholders

Outcome

- Report on the value of curated data resources to support global FAIR-ification efforts

Activity 2 - Establish guidelines for Community Database identification and monitoring

(leads: IT-UNIPD (Damiano Piovesan); members: DE-HITS (Ulrike Wittig), SE-CTH (Mihail Anton), EMBL-EBI (Melissa Harrison), CH-SIB (Julien Gobeill), IT-UNIPD (Silvio Tosatto), M1 - M36)

This task aims to establish a robust and simple procedure for the identification and badging of ELIXIR Community Databases. This entails landscape analysis, covering all ELIXIR Databases, based on Nodes' service delivery plans (SDPs) to establish simple minimum quality criteria for Community Databases. The identified criteria should be a checklist that does not require additional discussion or complex assessment to be applied. At the end of the process, a first iteration of the ELIXIR Community Database badge should be awarded to all data resources meeting the criteria.

Plan of work

- A landscape analysis of Node practices wrt to database delivery
- Workshop with stakeholders (e.g. Node Coordinators) to define Community Database criteria
- Checklist for community database badging

Outcome

- A report recommending a list of criteria to derive a uniformed analysis of all ELIXIR Data assets.
- A first list of badged Community Databases (at the end of the current work plan, i.e. 2026)

Activity 3 - Apply and adapt monitoring methodology for indicators

(leads: CH-SIB (Julien Gobeill); members: CH-SIB (Patrick Ruch), CH-SIB (Lucy Poveda), CH-SIB (Christophe Dessimoz), M1 - M36)

The current criteria to define ELIXIR CDR include various bibliometric indicators. Such statistical indicators include the counting of mentions, citations and database accession numbers (e.g., identifiers.org).

Plan of work

- Leverage node coordination to acquire a list of community databases from nodes
- Define a diverse sample of databases, maintained by several nodes, beyond CDRs (e.g., community databases) for testing the indicators
- Monitor KPI universe and leverage data liberation initiatives beyond Europe PMC (e.g., supplementary data files from WP43)

Outcome

- Recommendations to establish an improved list of KPI to support the evaluation of ELIXIR databases

Deliverable	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
D5.1	Report about the value of curated data resources to support global FAIR-ification efforts	CH-SIB	M18
D5.2	A report recommending a list of criteria for Community Databases	IT-UNIPD	M24
Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M5.1	Completed 2024 Periodic Review of existing ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases	ELIXIR-HUB	M11

M5.2	Completed 2025 call for new ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases	ELIXIR-HUB	M23
M5.3	Completed 2026 Periodic Review of existing ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases	ELIXIR-HUB	M35
M5.4	A first iteration of the Community Database selection process	IT-UNIPD	M36
M5.5	A proof of concept evaluation of the new KPIs	CH-SIB	M30

Table of Deliverables and Milestones

Deliverable / Milestone	Description	Responsible Institution	Due / Month
M2.1	M2.1 Definition of the parameters for the landscape analysis	EMBL-EBI	8
M5.1	Completed 2024 Periodic Review of existing ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases	ELIXIR-HUB	11
M1.1	Annual Data Platform meeting 1	DE-HITS	12
M3.3	M3.3 Use cases for APICURON evaluated	IT-UNIPD	12
D4.1	A report describing best practices of literature biocuration	CH-SIB	12
D1.1	Annual report 1 - on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	DE-HITS	13
M3.1	M3.1 Bioschemas entities for APICURON defined	FR-CNRS	15
D2.1	Description of landscape analysis including collection of user and repository requirements	EMBL-EBI	18
M3.4	M3.4 Outreach link established with relevant EU Projects (e.g. STEERS, EVERSE and GraspOS)	GR-ATHENA	18
D4.2	A workshop co-located in a known forum to report on	CH-SIB	18
D4.3	A large annotated dataset of literature	CH-SIB	18
D5.1	Report about the value of curated data resources to support global FAIR-ification efforts	CH-SIB	18
M2.2	M2.2 Writing event	CH-SIB	20
M5.2	Completed 2025 call for new ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases	ELIXIR-HUB	23
M1.2	Annual Data Platform meeting 2	IT-UNIPD	24
D2.2	Description of best practices in appropriate knowledge resources (e.g. RDMkit, FAIR Cookbook, FAIRsharing)	BE-VIB	24
D3.3	Report on engagement and gamification strategies, describing resource and people views	IT-UNIPD	24
M3.2	M3.2 Prototype for harvesting GitHub contributions implemented	SE-UU	24
M4.1	A demonstrator showing how annotations can be displayed in JATS/BioC	CH-SIB EMBL-EBI	24
D5.2	A report recommending a list of criteria for Community Databases	IT-UNIPD	24

D1.2	Annual report 2 - on the activities of the Platform (ExCo, AHM, monthly meeting, ad-hoc meeting)	IT-UNIPD	25
M2.3	M2.3 Following the work of activity 1 and activity 2 additional use cases (beyond ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP1 Task 2) have been selected to support further explorations into how the ISA-based solution can be expanded to support the emerging best practices for a wider range of domains/techniques and corresponding ELIXIR deposition databases	NO-UiO	30
D3.2	Demonstrator for expanded profiles providing rich statistics in APICURON	IT-UNIPD	30
M5.5	A proof of concept evaluation of the new KPIs	CH-SIB	30
D1.3	End Report	CH-SIB	36
M5.3	Completed 2026 Periodic Review of existing ELIXIR Core Data Resources and Deposition Databases	ELIXIR-HUB	35
D1.4	Drafted project plan for the next funding cycle in 2027-2028 ELIXIR Programme	DE-HITS IT-UNIPD CH-SIB	36
M1.3	Annual Data Platform meeting 3	CH-SIB	36
D2.3	Maturity model for data brokering services	BE-VIB	36
D2.4	A detailed description for the high-level technical proof of concept, demonstrating the feasibility and functionality of the proposed approach for data brokering	SE-UU	36
D2.5	Publication of the proposed solution(s) for data brokering in appropriate knowledge resources (e.g. RDMkit Tool assembly page and a FAIR Cookbook recipe)	BE-VIB	36
D3.1	Report on resources integrated in APICURON	IT-UNIPD	36
D3.4	Report on uptake of APICURON as an infrastructure service	IT-UNIPD	36
M5.4	A first iteration of the Community Database selection process	IT-UNIPD	36

Appendix A: Partner information

Institution	Contact Name
CH-SIB	Patrick Ruch
DE-HITS	Ulrike Wittig
IT-UNIPD	Silvio Tosatto
BE-ULB	Tom Lenaerts
BE-VIB	Flora D'Anna
CH-SIB	Christophe Dessimoz
CH-SIB	Julien Gobeill
CH-SIB	Lucy Poveda
CH-SIB	Monique Zahn
CH-SIB	Paul van Rijen
CH-SIB	Sverine Duvaud
DE-FZJ	Sebastian Beier
DE-IPK	Daniel Arend
ELIXIR-HUB	Fabio Liberante
ELIXIR-HUB	Gavin Farrell
EMBL-EBI	Aravind Venkatesan
EMBL-EBI	Claire O'Donovan
EMBL-EBI	Guy Cochrane
EMBL-EBI	Matt Jeffryes
EMBL-EBI	Melissa Harrison
EMBL-EBI	Ugis Sarkans
EMBL-EBI	Zahra Waheed
ES-CRG	Teresa D'Altri
FR-CNRS	Alban Gaignard
UK-UCAM	Valerie Wood
UK-UOXF	Allyson Lister
UK-UOXF	Philippe Rocca-Serra
GR-ATHENA	Thanasis Vergoulis
GR-AUTH	Christos Ouzounis
GR-AUTH	Fotis Psomopoulos
IT-UNIBO	Emidio Capriotti
IT-UNIBO	Paola Turina
IT-UNIPD	Adel Bouhraoua

IT-UNIPD	Alexander Monzon
IT-UNIPD	Damiano Piovesan
IT-UNIROMA2	Luana Licata
NO-UiO	Federico Bianchini
NO-UiO	Sveinung Gundersen
SE-CTH	Mihail Anton
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SE-UU	Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström
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